

They're called migratory internally lubricated thermoplastics. They provide lower friction and wear, and they eliminate the run-in period needed for conventional self-lubricating compounds. Their "secret ingredient" is silicone, which migrates to the wear surface during operation.

New Self-Lubricating Plastics Are Slipperier and Wear Better

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FREEDOM FROM MAINTENANCE is becoming increasingly important for the success of a design. Many products, such as portable power tools, appliance motors, and various automotive components, have achieved the goal of maintenance-free service by switching from metal to plastic bearings, gears, and other wear members.

In most of these cases, displacement of metal components has been based on performance, not on processing or material economy. Advantages include vibration damping, quietness of operation, light weight, corrosion resistance and, of course, self-lubricating characteristics. Despite all of these excellent design qualifications, conventional lubricated compounds also have limitations—which are eliminated in a new class of materials containing

Table 1—Wear and Friction Properties of Internally Lubricated Thermoplastics

Base Resin	Lubricant (%)			Wear Factor, K*	Coefficient of Friction		Limiting PV		
	Silicone	PTFE	PTFE and Silicone		Static	Dynamic	at 10 fpm	at 100 fpm	at 1,000 fpm
Acetal Copolymer	—	—	—	65	0.14	0.21	4,000	3,500	<2,500
	2	—	—	29	0.09	0.12	4,000	5,000	3,000
	—	20	—	17	0.07	0.15	10,000	12,500	5,500
	—	—	20	9	0.06	0.11	8,000	15,000	12,000
Nylon 6/6	—	—	—	200	0.20	0.28	3,000	2,500	>2,500
	2	—	—	40	0.09	0.09	3,000	6,000	9,000
	—	20	—	12	0.10	0.18	14,000	27,500	8,000
	—	—	20	6	0.06	0.08	14,000	30,000	12,000
Nylon 6/6 (30% glass)	—	15	—	16	0.19	0.26	17,500	20,000	17,000
Nylon 6/10 (30% glass)	—	15	—	15	0.23	0.31	20,000	15,000	12,000
Polycarbonate	—	—	—	8	0.17	0.18	20,000	15,000	12,000
	—	—	—	2,500	0.31	0.38	750	500	—
	—	15	—	75	0.09	0.15	15,000	20,000	10,500
Polystyrene	—	—	—	40	0.08	0.09	15,000	22,500	17,000
	—	—	—	3,000	0.28	0.32	750	1,500	—
	2	—	—	37	0.06	0.08	4,000	9,000	—

*A wear factor of $K = 1$ indicates a test condition that produces a wear volume of 1 in.³ of material in 1 hr at a load of 1 psi and a velocity of 1 fpm. Wear data presented here (to be multiplied by 10⁻¹⁰) were determined on a 0.900-in. ID x 0.125-in. OD plastic thrust washer operating at 50 fpm under a 40-psi load, against a 1040 steel washer with a 12-rms finish.

silicone that “migrates” to the wear surface during service.

Conventional Lubricated Plastics

The first thermoplastics with inherent self-lubricating qualities were nylon, acetal, and polytetrafluorocarbon (PTFE). Then came formulations that used PTFE, molybdenum disulfide, or graphite particles mixed with various resins to provide better lubrication and wear characteristics. These were improvements, but mechanical strength and dimensional stability of the internally lubricated thermoplastics (ILTPs) were often insufficient to meet performance requirements.

To minimize these deficiencies, reinforcing fibers—usually glass—were added. The reinforced compounds are several times stronger than unreinforced materials and are extremely stable in a wide range of service environments.

The search has continued for still better self-lubricating materials, for even the reinforced ILTP compounds have a deficiency that can be troublesome in some applications: In service, conventional internally lubricated thermoplastics require a period of time for the internal lubricant to become exposed and burnish over the wear surfaces. During this brief period, as a new bearing or wear member is put into service, contact of unlubricated surfaces occurs.

Migration is the Answer

The solution to this problem appears to lie in a new class of self-lubricating materials called migratory internally lubricated thermoplastics (MILTPs). Not only do these compounds eliminate the problems of initial run-in; they also have better wear and friction characteristics than the ILTPs.

The MILTP compounds are blends, or partial alloys, of a thermoplastic resin and a small percentage of a lower-molecular-weight polymer—sili-

cone. The unusual aspect of these compounds is that the silicone is sufficiently compatible with the base resin to form a partial alloy, yet it is not compatible enough so that it stays in the compound. The silicone moves to the surface of a molded or extruded part by two mechanisms: diffusion by random molecular movement, and exclusion from the matrix (migration) because of its limited compatibility. The result of this constant-bleed action is a continuous generation of a polymer film which serves as a boundary, or mixed-film, lubricant.

Tests of acetal copolymer and nylon 6/6 MILTP samples (thrust washer against steel) show that wear factor and coefficient of friction are reduced by 50% or more, compared with the unmodified resins, Table 1. Also, limiting pressure-velocity (PV) values increase at the higher test velocities.

One More Step: A further enhancement of wear and friction properties has been achieved by adding both migratory-type polymer lubricants (silicone)

Migratory or constant-bleed action of silicone in a migratory internally lubricated compound containing both PTFE and silicone. The two materials combine at the wear surface and form an extreme-pressure lubricant.

SELF-LUBRICATING PLASTICS

and particle-type internal lubricants. PTFE was selected because it has the lowest coefficient of friction (0.04 to 0.06) of the solid internal lubricants commonly used in thermoplastic compounds.

As these materials combine at the wear surface, they form a high-temperature grease. The PTFE acts both as a thickener and an extreme-pressure additive, and the silicone lubricant ensures continuous lubricity, both at startup and at high speeds.

The addition of migratory internal lubricant produces the greatest improvement on limiting *PV* at high velocities. This is to be expected because high-speed failure is more directly related to wear than is low-speed failure. In PTFE/silicone-lubricated acetal, for example, the *PV* limit more than doubles, compared with that of a straight PTFE-lubricated compound at 1,000 fpm, Table 1.

Several factors account for the deficiencies of gears and bearings made from resins without reinforcements and internal lubricants: 1. Wear rates are high under conditions of only moderate sliding pressure because surface asperities are fused at relatively low temperatures. 2. Because thermoplastics do not wet readily, boundary lubrication is difficult to maintain. 3. Low mechanical strength and poor dimensional stability make plain resins impractical for minimum-contact parts such as gear teeth. Internally lubricated thermoplastics correct the first two problems; reinforced, internally lubricated thermoplastics—and particularly those with migratory lubricants—take care of all three deficiencies.

These new compounds are already being used to mold wear members for textile machinery and mechanical parts for water meters. Numerous other applications are being evaluated.

Mechanical Properties: Properties of the MILTPs, other than those related to wear and friction, are nearly the same as those of the straight PTFE-filled materials, Table 2. In general, tensile and flexural properties are slightly lower, and impact strength tends to be slightly higher. Although tests have not yet been made involving thermal stability, this characteristic may be improved in the silicone-containing compounds. Another advantage

expected of these materials is easier processing—the silicone acts as a mold-release agent and can provide more efficient processing by extrusion.

Migration Rate: Two methods were used to investigate the rate of migratory lubrication of MILTPs at room temperatures. In the first, a test sample of nylon 6/6 containing 2% silicone was wet with water. The contact angle of a water drop was measured initially. Then the surface of the sample was wiped clean of the silicone, and contact angles of water drops were measured at regular intervals. Complete regeneration of the silicone was effected in 36 hr.

A second test was made on an acetal copolymer sample containing 2% silicone. The surface was wiped clean periodically. The greatest rate of migration occurred initially and appeared to reach equilibrium after 36 days. The specimen was then tested for wear properties; results were identical to those listed in Table 1.

Migration rate increases at higher temperatures. While complete test data are not yet available, it has been determined that about 15% of the silicone content of an acetal copolymer sample migrates to the surface in 36 days at 115 C.

Availability, Price: Although most data have been gathered on acetal and nylon MILTPs, other resins not normally considered for wear applications are also being tested with migratory internal lubricants. These include polystyrene, polycarbonate, ABS, and polypropylene. All are available, either as ready-to-mold compounds or as concentrates that can be mixed with the same resin.

Formulations of nylon, acetal, and polycarbonate (plus PTFE and silicone) now carry a price of \$5/lb for developmental quantities. Price for higher volume needs (1,000 lb or more) is expected to be in the \$3/lb range—about 20% higher than conventional PTFE-filled engineering thermoplastics.

For less critical applications, where lowest price is a major consideration and where nonlubricated resins won't do the job, compounds containing silicone only (no PTFE) are available. Costs, in volume quantities, range from \$1.50 to \$2.00/lb.

Table 2—Physical and Mechanical Properties of Internally Lubricated Thermoplastics

Base Resin	Specific Gravity	Water Absorption (%)	Tensile Strength (psi)	Tensile Elongation (%)	Flexural Strength (10 ³ psi)	Flexural Modulus (10 ³ psi)	—Impact Strength—	
							Notched (ft-lb/in.)	Unnotched
Acetal Copolymer								
20% PTFE	1.55	0.15	6,500	23.0	8.0	375	0.6	7.7
20% PTFE and Sil	1.52	0.16	6,000	37.0	7.7	360	0.7	7.6
Nylon 6/6								
20% PTFE	1.26	1.00	9,000	9.0	13.7	290	0.7	10.2
20% PTFE and Sil	1.18	0.80	9,600	5.5	13.6	250	0.9	9.1
30% glass, 15% PTFE	1.49	0.50	23,500	4.0	35.0	1,350	1.8	16.0
Nylon 6/10								
30% glass, 15% PTFE	1.45	0.15	20,000	4.0	29.0	1,150	2.2	20.0
30% glass, 15% PTFE and Sil	1.40	0.10	18,200	5.0	27.5	1,000	2.2	16.0